

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Derivation of a breeding value for persistency in German dairy cattle focusing on performance in extended lactations

Supplemental Table 1: Calo correlations¹ between different trait complexes to persistency based on gEBV of German females born 2021 from herd genotyping (estimation Dec. 2022)

gEBV²	trait complex/index	correlation to persistency
N		105,557
RZM	production yield	0.35
RZN	longevity	0.28
RZE	conformation	0.09
RZR	fertility	-0.10
RZhealth	direct health	0.18
RZKm	calving maternal	0.05
RZKd	calving direct	0.15
RZcalffit	calf fitness	0.00
RZG	total merit index	0.35

¹ Calo correlations = transformed gEBV correlation with calo's method (Calo et al. 1973)

² gEBV = genomic estimated breeding value; definition of indices in vit (2025)